

The Impact of Training & Development in Educational Institutions of Pakistan For Job Satisfaction and Employee Retention

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Employee Retention, Training and Development, Job Satisfaction.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5565085</p>	<p><i>Effective HRM practices play an important role in the prosperity of any organization. It is considered as the toughest task for every organization as it helps in achieving competitive edge. Talented employees are considered as an asset for the organization because they have the strong influence on the profitability and productivity of an organization. Today almost all of the educational institutions are facing the issue of employee retention and job satisfaction. The main focus of the study is to explore the connection between training and development, job satisfaction and employee retention among the academic staff of educational institutions of Pakistan. The study is quantitative in nature, in which close ended questionnaire was used for the data collection. Data has been collected from 150 respondents, who are the employees of different educational institutions via email keeping in consideration the current situation of Covid. The data was collected through questionnaire developed on Google doc and analyzed through SPSS software by using regression approach. Results and findings of this research showed that training and development have significant impact on job satisfaction and employee retention. Additionally the implications, limitations and recommendations for future research were discussed.</i></p>

Introduction

In this era of globalization and advance technology employee retention has become the most challenging task for any organization. In order to be competitive and profitable every organization should focus on retention strategies. At present, a lot of organizations especially the educational institution that includes the school, colleges and universities are going through this issue of high turnover and low employee job satisfaction which is extremely detrimental for them. Therefore every organization should retain their talented employees, it will also save money because attracting and selecting new employees is quite difficult and expensive process (Akhter & Tariq, 2020).

Highly skilled and talented employees are considered as the most valuable asset of an organization because they have an uninterrupted influence on firm's productivity, profitability and reputation. If the performance of employees is positive then it will lead the organization towards the path of success and achievements but if the performance of employees is negative then it will lead towards the failure, that's why employees are called backbone of any organization (Nguyen & Duong, 2020).

Education focuses on growth and strengthening of human capital. In education sector the growth and development of human resource means focusing on those employees that are playing the main role in the education system. Training and development of all those people that are involved in education should our supreme priority so they can do their jobs more effectively and efficiently. Education comes under the service industry and teachers are the most precious and significance part of it, as without teachers not a single educational institution can survive. In order to offer the best education, the training and development and job satisfaction of teachers is very essential (Paposka & Kumar, 2019).

Employee retention has become the basic need for every organization in this time period of advance technology mainly in the educational institutions of Pakistan. As the number of schools, college and universities is increasing day by day it creates the shortage of highly skilled faculty and employees have more options so they are keep switching their jobs for better options. The procedure of retention begins with the selection of right people and execution of several strategies in order to keep employees active and inspired.

The popularity of the concept "retention" is continuously increasing day by day because of new trends, globalization and greater number of job opportunities (Malik, Baig & Manzoor, 2020).

The capability of an organization to hold it employees is known as employee retention. It is the combination of plan of actions, arrangements and strategies that are designed to keep the employees for the longer period of time. It is beneficial for upgrading competitive advantage and enhancing organization's cognitive abilities (Aleem & Bowra, 2020). Employee turnover is an obstacle in the success of every organization that's why everyone is trying a way hard to tackle with this issue. Because when an employee leaves the organization it

will be a great loss as he will take all the secrets, skills and values etc. with himself, that can be used by the competitors, which is extremely detrimental for the company (Singh, 2019).

Job satisfaction is defined the amount of pleasure or joy associated with the job. It is related to employee's individual evaluation about certain aspects of job. It is the significant component and it is related to employee performance and commitment as well. There are very insufficient number of education institution that gives priority to job satisfaction which results in increase of employee absenteeism and turnover (Sumayya, Kumari, Rashid, & Shakir (2020). Employee job satisfaction is based on how they have been treated in the organization like if the policies that have made by the management of organization are creating a disagreement with the expectations of employees than obviously there is low level of satisfaction. Employees consider themselves as a part of organization and have some expectation towards the company and its administration. They think that their opinion should be included in the decision-making process, but when they are not included then it will create negative impact on employee and also lower their motivation and satisfaction level (Khan et al., 2016). Job satisfaction is the essential component that's why almost every theory of motivation and employee commitment have acknowledge its worth and almost all the dominant theories are associated with job satisfaction like Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Social learning theory and Herzberg's Two Factor Theory. Many others have emphasized on job satisfaction and its impact on the organization (Jehanzeb&Mohanty, 2018).

Training and development are defined as an effort to increase organization's efficiency and effectiveness through learning, generally by changing employee's behavior and by enhancing their skills, knowledge and abilities. Recently training and development has become extremely appealing to almost every organization who wants to increase its performance and productivity (Macali, Jesus &Almari, 2019).

Training is supposed to be an expense for the company but in reality, investing in training and development have proved to be beneficial for the organization. Previous researchers discover that there is strong influence of training on commitment and constant commitment has negative relation with employee turnover (Khan, 2018).

According to an earlier study by Omoikhudu (2017) stated the training have the greater impact on employee's decision to quit or to hold on. Additionally, it says that employees feel more delighted, satisfied and cheerful when their performance is being appreciated by managers or supervisors which make them more active and motivated toward their roles. The result of recent study by Chaudhary & Bhaskar (2016) disseminates that the companies who incorporate training and development practices at their workplace will have greater employee satisfaction and decreased turnover.

Hence the aim of this investigation is to examine the connection between training and development, job satisfaction and retention among the employees of education sector. It will be a source of guidance for all the educational institutions, especially for human resource professionals and managers that how to attract, satisfy and retain the talented employees for the longer period of time through training.

Literature Review

Due to the tremendous technological advancement and globalization the world has become the smaller place. In this scenario organizations should make themselves competitive enough in order to compete with other organization and the outcomes of globalization. The competitiveness of a firm can be measured by the level the knowledge, skills and abilities possessed by their employees (Karim, Choudhury & Latif, 2019).

Underpinning and Supporting Theories/Models

In order to discuss the relationship between training and development, job satisfaction and employee retention Maslow hierarchy of needs theory act as a theoretical foundation theory. According to Maslow there are five basic needs that are physiological, safety, love, esteem and self-actualization. This theory supports training programs and considers it a basic need for an employee in order to perform their job effectively, When an organization take care of their employees training and development or provide them with specific training that is needed by them to perform a specific job role, which will help them to perform their job easily, eventually it will decrease the stress level of an employee and this will create and sense of belongingness and loyalty. This results in higher employee satisfaction and strong employee commitments which in result decrease the turnover intentions.

Training and Development

It is defined as the systematic procedure to prosper and strengthen the knowledge, talent, expertise, potential and capabilities of employees for the sake of enhancing the efficiency of the organization. It is the one of the most important HRM practices. It is the cluster of different plans and activities that leads to the uninterrupted learning

and evolving of job and career affiliated expertise. In past researches it has been communicated that there is positive relation between training and development and retention (Fletcher, Alfes& Robinson, 2016).

Training and growth practices protect the organization from high employee turnover. Adjusting the tasks of employees with the aims and objectives of organization, providing them the training they required will increase their loyalty and desire to be with the organization. Previous studies declare that training & development directly related to employee retention (Karimi, 2019).

Training is the step by step process that empowers the learner to attain the goals of the organization. Almost all of the researchers admit that the training and development of employees have vigorous effect on the achievements of both employee and organization. And it has been reported by the American Society of Training and Development that around \$126 billion is spent by the organizations on training and development of employees on yearly basis (Patara, 2019).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is explained as the amount of pleasure and gratification an employee feels and the degree of constructive opinion they have regarding their job. It is connected to those concerns that are the first and foremost priority of employees. It is often recognized as an energetic response of employees for the job or specific role of the job (Sumayya&Raziq, 2019).

Motivation is the key factor behind the job satisfaction and high commitment. Organizations should lead their employees in way that they remain motivated and inspired, so they will get satisfied with their job and get strongly committed towards organization for the extended time period. Job satisfaction is also defined as the feeling of an employee about his/her job which is demonstrated by the attitude and behavior of an employee (Murtiningsih, 2020).

Positive and negative attitudes of employees toward their jobs can easily tell us that whether they are satisfied or not or to what extent they like or dislike their jobs. Job satisfaction is viewed as the major factor in order to evaluate the proficiency and successfulness of any organization, that's why every organization should prioritize employee's needs, wants and desires to make them satisfied. As the employee is satisfied, it will make him happy that consequently makes him more productive and it will lead the organization towards the path of success (Jalagat, 2016).

Employee Retention

Employee retention is the way of inspiring and motivating employees in order to make them highly committed with the company for the prolonged time period or up till the fulfillment of any particular task. It is also defined as the process of holding highly skilled and talented employees for extended time period. It plays significant part in the success of an organization (Temba, 2020). Employee plays an important role and it is considered as the asset of an organization. Employee retention is an approach acquired by the organizations in order to sustain the highly productive employees and maintain the proper functioning of operations simultaneously (Mary & Susan, 2017). Now-a-days several organizations are going through the problem of employee turnover. Retaining talented personnel is very essential in order to be successful in competitive surroundings (Ivana, 2020).

Employee retention is directly connected to the plans and strategies construct and execute by the human resource management of the organization. Additionally, it is the responsibility of an organization to fulfill the needs of their employee professionally and morally (Elsafy&Ragheb, 2020). Employee retention depends on the motivation of employees that means the increase in motivation level of employees consequently enhance the retention of employees. Motivation is comprising of intrinsic and extrinsic elements, both of them are substantial for boosting the efficiency and effectiveness (Sharafi, Hassan &Alam, 2018). The impulsive force behind the proficiency and productivity of an employee is motivation. Employees with higher level of motivation are more satisfied which ultimately increase the productivity of the organization. Highly skilled employees are the most crucial part of any organization, and they should be maintaining and retain properly. Additionally, when employees are not satisfied with their current job, employer or organization they began to switch, which ultimately leads to the wastage of investment that the organizations have made on these employees while hiring and recruiting process (Dhanya&Prashath, 2019).

Training and Development and Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is the amount of willingness and positivity that an employee possess toward his/her job. Basically, it is the feeling of an employee about the job, it can be good or bad, this feeling than reveals that whether the employee is satisfied or not. There are several factors that transform or modify the employee job satisfaction. It is the most significant component because it is related to the increased performance and dedication of an employee towards the organization. Different organizations are going through problems of non-attendance and high turnover due to the dissatisfaction of employees with their current job (Sareen, 2018). Training and development practice are an effort made by the organizations in order to prepare the employees for

current job or task by giving them specific knowledge and skills required to perform the job. It is a learning process. It is playing an outstanding role in strengthening employee's job satisfaction (Murtiningsih, 2020). Nuhu et al. (2018) examines the correspondence between training and job satisfaction, the outcomes of the research reveal that training and development have direct relation with job satisfaction. It plays an important part in the success of every business. Additionally, it states that goals and achievement are based on employee happiness, fulfillment and satisfaction which in turn contribute to development and profitability of an organization, increasing efficiency and quality of work. In this competitive environment the survival of any organization depends upon its capability to train its human capital to be more creative that will enhance the organizational performance and to be a market leader. Training plays a vital role in the development of employee satisfaction.

According to study of Sothy (2019) for the sake of strengthening job satisfaction training practices have been used. Faridi, Baloch, and Wajidi (2017) investigate the connection that exist within training and development and job satisfaction, the results disseminate that the variables have strong connections with each other. The results of the study conducted by Pržulj and Vještica (2017) shows that job satisfaction is highly influenced by training. On the basis of discussion of previous researches following hypothesis has been formulated.

H1: There is a positive impact of training and development on job satisfaction.

Training and Development and Employee Retention

Employee Retention is defined as keeping the talented and skilled employees in a way that they will become highly committed with the organization for a longer time period. Recognition and appreciation will make the employees more loyal and committed towards the organization. Sometimes retention is defined as a complex idea as there is not only one solution for retaining the employees. Retention is influenced by number of elements and organizational commitment is the most important and common from all of them. Additionally, employee wants to be with the firm for the longer time when they feel that the organization is acknowledging and investing in their employees, ultimately it will create the sense of belongingness which in result strengthens the commitment. Training is the technique used by organizations for the sake of making their employees more productive with extra knowledge and expertise. In addition to this it is beneficial for the organizations as well in order to retain their capable and highly skilled employees (Jwu et al., 2018).

The study conducted by Damei (2020) affirms that there is strong connection between training and development and employee retention. Ogalo (2018) examine the relationship between training and employee retention. The findings of the research disclosed that training has strong effect on retention of employees. The outcome of the research conducted by Meirinhos, Abrunhosa and Martins (2018) declares that training and development is one of those HRM practices that have the powerful impact on employee retention.

The research conducted by Bibi, Ahmad and Majid (2018) says that may be training and development helps in retaining employees but on the other side of picture it will also make the employees attractive to other organizations by increasing their skills, knowledge and abilities. Additionally, it has also been argued that retention is not positively affected by training and development, that's why from the above discussion it is been concluded that there is no comprehensible and logical clarification about the nature of connection between training and retention. As different studies concluded different results that's why further exploration is needed to explain the connection between both. On the basis of discussion of previous researches following hypothesis has been formulated.

H2: There is a positive impact of training and development on employee retention.

Methodology

This research focuses on the employees specifically the teaching staff (i.e. lecturers, assistant lecturer, associate lecturer and professors) of educational institution located all over Pakistan. it was not practically possible to get the accurate number of employees working in education sector of Pakistan that's why the researcher preferred to go for convenience based non-probability technique for collection of data (Abbas, 2020).

A sample size of 384 respondents was selected for the purpose of this study. According to Krejcie and Morgan (1970) this sample size is good enough for a population as large as 1 million. But due to the situation of pandemic and very short time period, after getting permission from Research Facilitation Unit (RFU) the data was collected from 150 respondents. For collecting the data researcher develop the close ended questionnaire on Google docs. By considering the current situation of Covid and convenience of researcher and respondent both, as it is very difficult to visit personally that's why the link of the questionnaire has been sent to different employees via email, who works as a teacher/lecturer in any educational institution of Pakistan.

Instrument of Data Collection

In this study questionnaire is designed on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “1= strongly disagree” to “5= strongly agree” for the sake of collecting all the quantitative data. It is incorporated of four sections. The first section is based on information of demographic features followed by measures of training and development, job satisfaction and employee retention respectively. In developing the instrument, the measurement scales were selected from validated sources that were used in previous studies. Employee retention was measured by using eight items taken from the research of Bibi et al. (2018).

Job satisfaction was measured by using five items adapted from the instrument of Chaudhary & Bhaskar (2016) and the two items were selected from the research of Fletcher et al. (2018). Finally training and development was measured by using the five items from the study of Bibi et al. (2018).

Results and Findings

Descriptive Profile of Data

The respondents were requested to share their demographic information which includes name of respondents, age, gender, education and nature of employment level in educational institution.

Table 1 Demographics

Variables		N	Mean
Gender	F	100	66.7
	M	50	33.3
Age	21- 25	53	35.3
	26-30	50	33.3
	31-35	26	17.3
	36-40	15	10.0
Education	Bachelors or equivalent	57	38.0
	Masters or equivalent	86	57.3
	PhD	7	4.7
Nature of Employment	Lecturer	105	70
	Assistant professor	38	25.3
	Professor	7	4.7
Total		150	100

Table 1 interpret that gender distribution was male and female in which female respondents were 66.7% (100) and male respondents were 33.3% (50). Respondents were given five age brackets from which they have to select their category. The first age distribution category was the age bracket between 21 to 25 years, which was selected by 35.3% respondents. 33.3% of the sample was among the ages of 26 and 30, 17.3% between 31 and 35, 10.0% between 36 and 40, 4.0% was above the age of 40. The largest percentage of respondents belongs to 21-25 year's age categories. The lowest percentage of respondents belongs to over 40 year's age categories. Respondents were provided with three level of education from which they had to pick and choose their category. The first age education distribution category is Bachelors or equivalent, which was selected by 57 respondents making up a percentage of 38.0%. Second option that is Masters or equivalent was selected by 86 respondents making up a percentage of 57.3%. Lastly, third option that is PhD was selected by 7 respondents making up a percentage of 4.7% of the total sample. Master's degree holder's accounts for the highest percentage and Doctorate degree holder's accounts for the lowest percentage. Respondents were provided with three options from which they had to pick and choose their category. The first category is lecturer, which was selected by 105 respondents making up a percentage of 70.0%. Second option that is Assistant professor was selected by 38 respondents making up a percentage of 25.3%. Third option that is Professor was selected by 7 respondents making up a percentage of 4.67%.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics of each variable is given below:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Training and Development	150	1.60	5.00	3.5160	.83426
Job Satisfaction	150	1.71	4.86	3.4295	.60076
Employee Retention	150	2.50	4.50	3.3700	.33805

The table above shows the mean values of the variables. According to the table, training and development has the highest mean value (3.516) followed by Job satisfaction (3.429), and Employee retention (3.370). As the researcher has adopted five-point Likert scales where 1 show strongly disagrees and 5 shows strongly agree. These mean values signify that the average response for each variable is neutral.

Validation of Model

Table 3. Reliability Statistics

Construct	No of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Training and development	5	0.907
Job Satisfaction	7	0.751
Employee Retention	8	0.895
Overall Reliability	20	0.801

Table 3 shows the Cronbach's alpha values. The variables with Cronbach's alpha value 0.7 or greater are considered as reliable and it shows that the data is reliable and consistent. Here all the variables have Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.7 which proves that the data is reliable and consistent. Additionally, the overall reliability of all the construct and items is greater than 0.7.

Hypothesis Testing

In this study there are two dependent variables so that is why regression analysis has been performed separately for each dependent variable.

H1: There is a positive impact of training and development on job satisfaction.

Table 4a Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.658 ^a	.433	.429	.45398

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training_and_development

Table 4b ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23.272	1	23.272	112.918	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.503	148	.206		
	Total	53.775	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Training_and_development

Table 4c. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.764	.161		10.951	.000
	Training_and_development	.474	.045	.658	10.626	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

In H1 training and development has been taken as an independent variable whereas Job satisfaction as a dependent variable. ANOVA table tells us about the significance of model, as the significant value of ANOVA is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which proves that the model is significant or the model is fit. On the other hand, value of R is 0.658 or 65.8% which means that there is 65.8% correlation between training and development and job satisfaction. Whereas the value of R-square is 0.433 or 43.3% which shows that there is 43.3% variation in dependent variable i.e. job satisfaction explained by independent variable i.e. training and development. Additionally, the value of Beta is positive (0.474) which shows that there is positive impact of training and development on job satisfaction.

H2: There is a positive impact of training and development on employee retention

Table 5a. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.332 ^a	.110	.104	.31999

a. Predictors: (Constant), Training_and_development

Table 5b ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.873	1	1.873	18.293	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.154	148	.102		
	Total	17.028	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee_retention

b. Predictors: (Constant), Training_and_development

Table 5c. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.897	.114		25.522	.000

Training_and_developm ent	.134	.031	.332	4.277	.000
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a. Dependent Variable: Employee_retention

In H2 training and development has been taken as an independent variable whereas employee retention as a dependent variable. ANOVA table tells us about the significance of model, as the significant value of ANOVA is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which proves that the model is significant or the model is fit. On the other hand, value of R is 0.332 or 33.2% which means that there is 33.2% correlation between training and development and employee retention. Whereas the value of R-square is 0.110 or 11.0% which shows that there is 11.0% variation in dependent variable i.e. employee retention as explained by independent variable i.e. training and development. Additionally, the value of Beta is positive (0.134) which shows that there is positive impact of training and development on job satisfaction.

Conclusion

Retaining highly skilled workforce and employee job satisfaction is always considered as the biggest challenge for every organization. The purpose of this research is to identify and examine the impact of training and development on job satisfaction and employee retention in education institutions of Pakistan. The finding of this research has been concluded with the acceptance of both the hypothesis that is H1 and H2, which shows that there is positive relation between training and development, job satisfaction and employee retention. Training and development have positive impact on both job satisfaction and employee retention. Thus, educational institutions should focus on the training and development of their employees in order to make them satisfied and retain them for the longer period of time.

Discussions

This research study was designed to investigate the impact of training and development on job satisfaction and employee retention, this study only targets the employees of education industry of Pakistan. The results of this study disseminate that there is a significant positive relationship between training and development, job satisfaction and employee retention. The findings of this study are harmonious with the results of previous research of Faridi, Baloch, and Wajidi (2017) which shows that there is strong positive connection between training and development and job satisfaction, which means that when an organization provide the required training to their employees it will decrease their stress level and make them more satisfied. The findings were also supported by Pržulj and Vještica (2017) which says that job satisfaction is highly influenced by training. Additionally, the finding of this research also declares that there is positive relationship between training and development and employee retention. These finding are consistent with the results of previous researches of Damei (2020) and Ogalo (2018) which indicates that when employees receive training from their organization it will increase employee loyalty and commitment, in result of this employee will become loyal to the organization and stay there for longer period of time.

Moreover these research finding are also supported by Maslow hierarchy of needs theory, This theory supports training programs and considers it a basic need for an employee in order to perform their job effectively, When an organization take care of their employees training and development or provide them with specific training which will help them to perform their job easily, eventually it will decrease the stress level of an employee and this will create and sense of belongingness and loyalty. This results in higher employee satisfaction and strong employee commitments which in result decrease the turnover intentions.

Implications

In the light of the findings of this research there are few recommendation and implications for the human resource managers and policy makers of education institutions of Pakistan. As the HR professionals and policy makers are responsible for allocating the resources and retaining employees, the findings of the current study recommends that training and development is one of the main sources of strengthening employee retention. So that's why the policy makers should design the proper training programs for their faculty members in order to make them satisfied and retain them for longer period of time.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

In spite of these good findings, this study still got some unavoidable limitation. Despite of the fact that this study was designed attentively, the time period for conducting the research was not adequate enough for the researcher to incorporate and observe a large number of respondents from different areas of the country. The data was gathered from 150 respondents only due to the situation of pandemic and most importantly because of very short time period, so future researcher should study the bigger sample size in order to get more generalized results. Secondly this study only focuses on employees of education industry, so in future other industries such as services and manufacturing industries should be taken in to consideration. Additionally, this study only focuses on training and development as a predictor of job satisfaction and employee retention, but the future

researchers can go for several other variables that also predict both variables. Moreover, lack of respondent's interest to fill the questionnaire was another limitation.

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